

Aqueous phase atmospheric oxidation of sulfur dioxide by oxygen : Role of trace atmospheric constituents – Metals, volatile organic compounds and ammonia[†]

K. S. Gupta

Atmospheric Chemistry Lab, Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : guptaks14@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : The oxidation of dissolved sulfur dioxide, i.e. sulfur(IV) by oxygen is an important pathway in the acidification of atmospheric waters. Over the years, much work has been done in our laboratory on this important atmospheric reaction. The catalytic role of transition metal ions, viz. Fe^{III}, Mn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ag^I, Os^{VIII} and Pd^{II} has been examined. The role of surface catalysis on this reaction in suspensions of CoO, C₂O₃, CuO, Cu₂O, MnO₂, Ni₂O₃, CdO, CdS, MgO, SiO₂, PbO₂, free fall atmospheric dust, fly ash, rock and mineral powders, lime stone etc. has been examined. It was shown for the first time that ammonia and ammonia ions – important trace atmospheric constituents – inhibit the oxidation of dissolved SO₂ if pH ≥ 7 and [NH₃]_T exceeds a particular value (~ 5 × 10⁻⁵ mol L⁻¹).

Keywords : Acid rain, sulfur(IV), autoxidation, kinetics, catalysis, inhibition, metal ions, ammonia.

Introduction

The atmospheric oxidation of sulfur and nitrogen oxides, in both gas and aqueous phases, is a major cause of acidification of atmospheric waters, such as rain water, cloud water, fog, mist etc. and, therefore, of acid rain¹⁻⁶. The major sulfur-based acid rain precursors are SO₂, H₂S and CH₃SCH₃. The major atmospheric oxidants, responsible for the oxidation of acid rain precursors, are hydroxyl radicals (OH), hydrogen peroxy radicals (HO₂), hydrogen peroxide, ozone and oxygen. The former four are formed as a result of the photochemical/thermal secondary reactions in atmosphere³. The radicals OH and HO₂ are the important atmospheric oxidants in the gas phase and hydrogen peroxide, ozone and oxygen are important in the aqueous phase. The oxidation of sulfur(IV) by oxygen, generally referred to as autoxidation, is very slow. However, it is strongly catalyzed by metal ions even in trace quantities as are found in atmospheric waters^{3,6}. Interestingly, this reaction is strongly inhibited by organic compounds⁶, many of which are found in atmosphere.

The catalytic sulfur(IV) – autoxidation contributes significantly to enhancement in rain water acidity. This necessitated detailed kinetics and mechanistic studies on these systems and the determination of rate constants for atmospheric modeling. Because of this atmospheric importance, the sulfur(IV) autoxidation has been the subject of number of kinetics studies under variety of reaction conditions^{1,3-9}. The details are available in books, monographs, reviews and papers. Of these, the important ones are due to Brandt and Eldik¹, Calvert³, Schwartz⁵, Martin⁶, Hoffmann and Jacob⁷, Hoffmann and Boyce⁸, Kuo *et al.*⁹, Herrmann¹⁰, Huie¹¹, Gupta *et al.*¹², Huie and Neta¹³, Huie and Peterson¹⁴, Huie and Sieck¹⁵.

This review is concerned mainly with the role of metals, ammonia and VOCs on the oxidation of sulfur(IV) by oxygen – the area in which we have been active.

Trace atmospheric constituents

Transition metals :

There are a large number of studies, which highlight the role of transition metals and their complexes in

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multiphase atmospheric chemistry¹⁻⁸. In a recent review, Deguillaume *et al.*¹⁶ have collated and analyzed the results of measurements of the concentrations of transition metal ions in various atmospheric aqueous phases such as wet, aerosols, clouds, fog, rain and snow. The significant concentrations of transition metal have been found and the source of these metals is the dissolution of the soluble fraction of aerosols in aqueous phase. The reactivity of the metals depends on many factors such as pH, their oxidation state, concentration and speciation. The concentrations of transition metals in rain water samples of Jaipur city have also been determined¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

Volatile organic compounds :

A large number of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) such as hydrocarbons, alcohols, carboxylic acids, aldehydes, terpenes, phenols²⁰ and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)²¹ etc., are found in trace amounts in atmosphere. The VOCs and other organics take part in many photochemical and thermal reactions in atmosphere and also influence the atmospheric chemistry of sulfur dioxide.

Ammonia/Ammonium ions :

Ammonia is an important trace atmospheric constituent and therefore understanding its effect on atmospheric oxidation of dissolved SO₂ is important. The ammonium ion concentration and pH ranges in rain water samples at different locations in India are : [NH₄⁺]_T = (3.7-127.5) × 10⁻⁶ (Agra)²²; 96 × 10⁻⁶ (Pune)²³; 147 × 10⁻⁶ (Delhi)²⁴; (1.7-220) × 10⁻⁶ (Ahemdabad)²⁵; (15.2-154.4) × 10⁻⁶ (Gopalpura)²⁶; (81.1-107.7) × 10⁻⁶ and (81.1-107.7) × 10⁻⁶ mol L⁻¹ (Dayalbagh)^{27,28}; pH ranges, 6.2-7.7 (Agra)^{22,27,28}; 6.3-7.6 (Pune), 7.2 (Delhi), 5.2-8.2 (Ahemdabad), 7.0-8.5 (Jaipur)²⁶.

Sulfur dioxide :

Ambient SO₂ concentrations are found generally in the range 1-20 ppb. In Jaipur city, the reported SO₂ lies in the range 2.5-10 ppb²⁹. SO₂ (g) is much more soluble in water than O₂ (g) and many other gases. Dissolved SO₂ exists mostly in three forms, SO₂.H₂O, HSO₃⁻ and SO₃²⁻, hereafter referred to as sulfur(IV), governed by the equilibria (1-5)⁶.

A small fraction exists as metabisulfite ion³⁰, S₂O₅²⁻.

Reactivity of aqueous S^{IV} strongly depends upon its speciation. In general, the reactivity pattern is SO₃²⁻ > HSO₃⁻ > SO₂.H₂O^{31,32}. In case of oxidation by H₂O₂ this pattern is inverted⁶.

Based on the equilibria (1-3) the equilibrium distribution of dissolved S^{IV} can be expressed by the following equation⁶.

$$[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] = [\text{SO}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}](1 + K_{d(1)}[\text{H}^+])^{-1} + K_{d(1)}K_{d(2)}[\text{H}^+]^{-2} \quad (5)$$

The eq. (5) shows that the solubility of SO₂ in water increases with increase in pH. And the nature of species of S^{IV} present depends on pH. For example in the pH range 4.0-5.6, the major species is HSO₃⁻ and above pH 7.0, SO₃²⁻ is the dominant species.

Aqueous phase autoxidation of sulfur(IV)

The uncatalyzed oxidation (i.e. in the absence of any catalyst added from outside) of sulfur(IV)

by oxygen (eq. (6)) is slow, but the metal ions, such as iron(II/III)^{1,6}, copper(II)¹, manganese(II)¹, cobalt(III)/cobalt(II)¹ and, to some extent, nickel(II), which are present as impurities in trace amounts in all water samples strongly catalyze sulfur(IV) autoxidation and, therefore, the observed sulfur(IV) oxidation rates in laboratory and atmospheric waters are actually trace metal catalyzed⁶⁻⁸. The evidence for this has been provided^{6,33} via a study of the effect of organics as discussed later. Silver(I)^{34,35}, osmium(VIII)³⁶ and palladium(II)³⁷ are other reported catalysts for this reaction.

Although, the kinetics of the uncatalyzed reaction has been studied repeatedly previously^{6,33,38,39}, to understand some other aspects of this reaction, it has been reinvestigated by us recently⁴⁰. Consistent with previous reports, in our study also, in the absence of any added inhibitor, the kinetics of the uncatalysed reaction in laboratory water was defined by eq. (7).

$$R_0 = k_0[S^{IV}] \quad (7)$$

where R_0 is the initial rate and k_0 is the first order rate constant. To explain the inhibitory effect of organics, a radical mechanism was first postulated by Backstrom⁴¹ involving SO_3^- and SO_5^- radicals. Subsequently, it has been revised with the inclusion of sulfate ion radical⁴², SO_4^- , as in the following mechanism^{7,8,40}.

Initiation :

Propagation :

Oxidation :

Termination :

The oxidation of sulfur(IV) by O_2 by using rain water samples as medium has also been studied²⁶.

Transition metal ion catalysis

Among the transition metals commonly found in atmospheric waters, iron, manganese and copper are considered to be the metals of major importance and cobalt and nickel of minor importance as catalysts in multi phase tropospheric sulfur(IV) chemistry. Incidentally, the catalytic autoxidation studies on aquatic sulfur dioxide are characterized by inconsistent reaction rates, rate laws and pH dependences^{1,7,8}. This has resulted in widely different rate laws being proposed for the same system. This led us to undertake the detailed studies on the kinetics of

iron(III)^{9,43}, manganese(II)⁴⁴, copper(II)^{45,46}, nickel(II)⁴⁷, silver(I)^{35,36}, osmium(VIII)³⁶ and palladium(II)³⁷ catalyzed sulfur(IV) autoxidation. Here the results of only Fe^{III}-catalyzed autoxidation⁴³ shall be briefly mentioned and details of catalysis by other metal ions can be seen in the cited papers.

Iron(III)-catalysis :

Iron-catalyzed reaction has been studied repeatedly and reviewed extensively^{9,48}. Most of the detailed studies⁴⁸ pertain to low pH region (0–3.5) in which the reaction rate is independent of VOCs' presence. On the other hand, this reaction displays strong inhibition⁴⁹ of the rate by VOCs, when pH is greater than 3.5. Obviously, the reaction appears to follow radical mechanism in the region of high pH (>3.5) and a non-radical mechanism in the region of low pH (<3.5). Recently, the kinetics of this reaction has been reinvestigated⁴⁴ by us in acetate buffered medium (pH 5.27–5.70). The kinetics was defined by rate law (18), which is same as reported earlier⁹.

$$\{-d[S^{IV}]/dt\} = k_{cat}[S^{IV}] = k_{Fe}[Fe^{III}][S^{IV}][H^+]^{-1} \quad (18)$$

As reported earlier, the addition of ethanol^{49,50} led to a sharp reduction in the rate in accordance with the rate law :

$$k_{cat} = A/(B + C [\text{ethanol}])$$

To explain the inhibition, the radical mechanism (19–26) involving a number of possible pathways^{48–52} has been proposed⁴³. The relative importance of different pathways in Fe^{III}-catalyzed reactions has been discussed by Warneck⁵³.

In above mechanism, X represents an impurity or wall-surface.

Assuming that total iron(III), $[Fe^{III}]_T$, is present as Fe^{III} and $[Fe^{III}(SO_3^{2-})]$ only, from the mechanism the rate law (27) was obtained.

$$R_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_5 k_1 K_d K_1 [\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]_T [\text{SO}_3^{2-}] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]}{(k_6 + k_7 [\text{ethanol}])(1 + K_1 [\text{SO}_3^{2-}]) (K_d + [\text{H}^+])} \quad (27)$$

The reaction is first order in $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ and this requires the inequality $K_1 [\text{SO}_3^{2-}] \gg 1$ to be valid, which would be true only if K_1 is assumed to have a high value. Since the value of K_d is reported to be 6.4×10^{-8} (25 °C)⁶, so in the pH range of this study $[\text{H}^+] \gg K_d$ shall hold. Based on these assumptions, the rate law (27) reduced to eqs. (28–29), which fully explained the observed experimental rate laws (28, 29).

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = \frac{k_5 k_1 K_d [\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]}{(k_6 + k_7 [\text{ethanol}]) [\text{H}^+]} \quad (28)$$

and

$$k_{\text{Fe}} = k_5 k_1 K_d / \{ (k_6 + k_7 [\text{ethanol}]) [\text{H}^+] \} \quad (29)$$

Transition metal oxide catalysis

Several particulate catalysts such as Cu_2O ⁵⁴, CuO ⁵⁵, MnO_2 ⁵⁶, CoO ⁵⁷, Co_2O_3 ⁵⁸ and Ni_2O_3 ^{59,60} catalyze the sulfur(IV) autoxidation. Mining, metallurgical processes, soil, high temperature combustion, thermal power plants, industrial processes and other human activities are the major sources of these compounds. The catalysis of these reactions has been examined in both acid and alkaline media.

Acid medium : The kinetics of autoxidation of aqueous sulfur dioxide has been studied in the acetate buffered aqueous suspensions of CoO ⁵⁷, Co_2O_3 ⁵⁸, Ni_2O_3 ⁵⁹, CuO ⁵⁵ and MnO_2 ⁵⁶. The evidence has been provided to support that the catalysis by metal oxides is mainly due to particle surface. The kinetics results were in agreement with the rate law (30) :

$$R_{\text{obs}} = (k_1 + k_2 [\text{H}^+]^{-1}) [\text{catalyst}] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (30)$$

The CoO and Co_2O_3 catalyses were studied under varying O_2 partial pressure and the kinetics was found^{57,58} to be defined by eq. (31).

$$R_{\text{obs}} = (k_3 + k_4 [\text{H}^+]^{-1}) [\text{catalyst}] [\text{O}_2] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (31)$$

To explain the experimental results, the formation of surficial complexes among metal oxides, sulfur(IV) (SO_3^{2-} and HSO_3^-) and dioxygen has been assumed as in the following mechanism :

In a subsequent study, the effect of free radical scavenger, ethanol, on the rates of these reactions was found to be small⁴⁴. In the autoxidation mechanism, the adsorbed S^{IV} transfers its electron to matrix – M (where M = Cu, Mn, Ni, Co) and S^{V} so formed interacts with adjacently adsorbed O_2 , takes back an electron from matrix M and leaves off⁵⁵ as SO_5^{2-} .

A comparison of the rate constants showed the reactivity order to be : $\text{MnO}_2 > \text{CuO} > \text{Co}_2\text{O}_3 > \text{CoO} > \text{Ni}_2\text{O}_3$. Among these oxides, only MnO_2 is able to oxidize sulfur(IV) directly in the absence of oxygen^{56,61}.

Alkaline medium : In alkaline medium, the kinetics⁶² of CoO , Co_2O_3 and Ni_2O_3 catalyzed sulfur(IV) autoxidation conformed the rate law (40).

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = R_{\text{cat}} = AK_2[\text{catalyst}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] \frac{[\text{O}_2]}{(1 + K_2[\text{O}_2])} \quad (40)$$

The ethanol, which is a well known inhibitor for S^{IV} autoxidation decreased the rate and at 5×10^{-3} mol L^{-1} ethanol no perceptible reaction occurred during 1 h. In the presence of ethanol, kinetics followed the rate law (41) :

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = AK_2[\text{CoO}][\text{S}^{\text{IV}}][\text{O}_2] / \{ (1 + C [\text{ethanol}])(1 + K_2[\text{O}_2]) \} \quad (41)$$

or

$$k_{\text{inh}} = AK_2[\text{O}_2] / \{ (1 + C [\text{ethanol}]) (1 + K_2[\text{O}_2]) \} \quad (42)$$

A comparison of rate laws (40) and (41) shows : $k_{\text{inh}} = k_A / (1 + C [\text{ethanol}])$. And when ethanol is absent, k_{inh} is equal to k_A .

To explain the observed kinetics including the inhibition by ethanol, the following radical mechanism has been proposed for CoO -catalysis⁶². A similar mechanism can be written for Co_2O_3 -catalysis.

In the mechanism, no role was envisaged for O_2^- , because it is known to react with sulfur(IV) slowly⁶³. By assuming long chain hypothesis, the mechanism led to the derived rate law (53) :

$$R_{\text{cat}} = k_6 k_1 K_2 [-\text{Co}^{\text{II}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{O}_2] / \{ (1 + K_2 [\text{O}_2]) \{ k_7 [\text{X}] + k_8 [\text{alc}] \} \} \quad (53)$$

or

$$k_{\text{inh}} = k_6 k_1 K_2 [\text{O}_2] / \{ (1 + K_2 [\text{O}_2]) \{ k_7 [\text{X}] + k_8 [\text{alc}] \} \} \quad (54)$$

A comparison of experimental rate law (40) and derived rate law (54) shows that at fixed $[\text{O}_2]$, $C = k_8/k_7[\text{X}]$. Using this relationship and reported k_8 value⁴³ of $4.1 \times 10^7 \text{ mol L}^{-1} (25^\circ\text{C})$, from the experimental values of C 1.9×10^4 , CoO ; 4.0×10^3 , Co_2O_3 , the values of $k_7[\text{X}]$ were estimated to be : $2.5 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (CoO) and $1.2 \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Co_2O_3).

In the absence of ethanol, the rate law reduces to eq. (55).

$$k_A = k_6 k_1 K_2 [\text{O}_2] / \{ (1 + K_2 [\text{O}_2]) k_7 [\text{X}] \} \quad (55)$$

The chain length for CoO and Co_2O_3 reactions was calculated by using eq. (56).

$$\text{Chain length} = k_6 [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] / k_7 [\text{X}] \quad (56)$$

A comparison with chain length values $\{ (4.4-7.3) \times 10^3 \}$ reported for sulfur(IV) autoxidation⁶⁵ shows our values (CoO , 4.4×10^2 ; Co_2O_3 , 0.92×10^2) to be lower by an order of magnitude and this could be due to dependence of chain length on $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$. In presence of ethanol, the chain

length would be given by eq. (57) :

$$\text{Chain length} = k_6 [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] / \{ k_7 [\text{X}] (1 + k_8 [\text{ethanol}]) \} \quad (57)$$

which requires the chain length to decrease with increase in ethanol and the reaction to be inhibited as noted.

Ni_2O_3 -Catalysis was somewhat complicated and marked by observance of an induction period at $\text{pH} \geq 8.0$. The kinetics in detail was studied at $\text{pH} 7.05$ at which the induction period was absent. The rate increased only slightly on increasing $[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]$ in agreement with the rate law (58) :

$$-d[\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = R_{\text{cat}} = k_1 K_1 [\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_3] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{O}_2] / \{ 1 + K_1 [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] \} \quad (58)$$

where k_1 is an empirical rate constant and K_1 is the stability constant of $\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_3\text{-S}^{\text{IV}}$ complex. Interestingly, Ni_2O_3 -catalyzed reaction in alkaline medium was inhibited only slightly by ethanol.

$$R_{\text{cat}} = k_1 K_1 [\text{Ni}_2\text{O}_3] [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{O}_2] / \{ (1 + K_1 [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]) (1 + C [\text{ethanol}]) \} \quad (59)$$

The value of C was determined to be 2.0×10^2 , which could be due to competitive adsorption of ethanol and sulfur(IV) on Ni_2O_3 particle surface. The following mechanism involving two alternative slow steps has been proposed to explain the observed kinetics.

and/or

Catalysis by atmospheric dust, fly ash, CdO , MgO , SiO_2 , etc.

Atmospheric dust⁶⁶, fly ash^{66,67}, PbO_2 ⁶⁸, cadmium oxide⁶⁹, magnesium oxide⁷⁰, silica⁵⁵, ceramic⁷¹, limestone⁷², rocks and mineral powders⁷³ and glass⁷⁴, also

catalyze the autoxidation in their aqueous suspensions. The important features of these catalytic reactions are as follows.

(i) Cadmium oxide, magnesium oxides and lime stone are very efficient catalysts and there appears to be a linear relationship between pH_{zpc} and the rate of autoxidation. Obviously higher is the surface pH, greater is the catalytic activity of the oxides.

(ii) In most of the cases, a kinetics order of more than one in sulfur(IV) has been found. Thus the activated complexes of the stoichiometry, catalyst- $\text{S}^{\text{IV}}\text{-O}_2$ and catalyst- $2\text{S}^{\text{IV}}\text{-O}_2$ appear to be formed owing to the leaching of metal ions and/or surface catalysis.

The results of atmospheric dust, fly ash and rock and mineral powders are particularly important in understanding their role in acidification of atmospheric waters⁷⁵⁻⁷⁸.

Effect of ammonia/ammonium ions on uncatalyzed reaction

We were led to study the effect of ammonia on this reaction by chance⁴⁰. Our desire to study the effect of some trace atmospheric constituents on the oxidation of aqueous sulfur dioxide by O_2 in alkaline medium, using ammonia as buffer, led to an interesting observation, hitherto unreported, that the reaction is completely stopped when $[\text{NH}_3]_{\text{T}} > 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ and $\text{pH} \geq 7.0$. This finding, to our knowledge, till then had not been reported, although the influence of ammonia on this reaction had been studied repeatedly⁷⁹⁻⁸⁸. A literature search revealed the reporting of some interesting observations without any explanation on the effect of ammonia/ammonium ions on the rate of sulfur(IV) autoxidation earlier. Matsuura *et al.*⁸⁹ and Mishra and Srivastava⁹⁰ reported a strong reduction in autoxidation rate when $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_3$ was used in the place of Na_2SO_3 and Reinders and Vles⁹² found no oxidation of sulfite to occur in 1.0 mol L^{-1} ammonia solution.

The study of effect of ammonia at four different pH values showed the rate to decrease with increase in total ammonia concentration, $[\text{NH}_3]_{\text{T}}$. Further, with increase in pH, the intensity of the inhibition increased. The results indicated that at each pH, the inhibiting effect of ammonia became perceptible only when $[\text{NH}_3]_{\text{T}}$ exceeded a particular value and the $\text{pH} \geq 7.0$. The inhibitory effect of ammonia was in accordance with the well known eq. (67).

$$R_{\text{aut}} = k_0 [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]/(1 + B [\text{inh}]_{\text{T}}) \quad (67)$$

where B is the inhibition parameter and $[\text{inh}]$ represents the concentration of the inhibitor.

The effect of ammonium ions was similar. The R_0 and B values determined using ammonia and ammonium nitrate as starting materials were found to be almost the same. The values of B in unbuffered media were higher nearly by an order of magnitude than in buffered medium.

Following the mechanism of inhibition of Fe-catalyzed autoxidation proposed by Zajka and Pasiuk-Bronikowska⁹², and assuming the initiation by trace metal ion impurities present in the reaction mixture, the mechanism comprising steps (8-14, 68, 69) has been proposed.

Since the rapid reactions of SO_4^- radicals with $\text{NH}_3/\text{NH}_4^+$ are well known⁹³, assuming the scavenging of SO_4^- by $\text{NH}_3/\text{NH}_4^+$ the postulated mechanism⁴⁰ led to the rate law :

$$R_{\text{aut}} = \frac{(2k_p) R_i [\text{S}^{\text{IV}}]}{k_{\text{M}(n-1)}[\text{M}^{(n-1)+}] + [\text{NH}_3]_{\text{T}} (\alpha k_{\text{NH}_3} [\text{OH}^-] + \alpha k_{\text{NH}_4} K_b)/([\text{OH}^-] + K_b)} \quad (70)$$

where α is equal to $[\text{SO}_5^-]/[\text{SO}_4^-]$.

The value of B was shown to be defined by eq. (71).

$$B = \frac{(\alpha k_{\text{NH}_3} [\text{OH}^-] + \alpha k_{\text{NH}_4} K_b)}{([\text{OH}^-] + K_b) k_{\text{M}(n-1)} [\text{M}^{(n-1)+}]} \quad (71)$$

The equations were utilized to obtain the values of rate parameters under variety of reaction conditions (Table 1). Whereas, $k_{\text{NH}_3}/k_{\text{NH}_4}$ value in buffered medium is seen to be slightly higher, the value in unbuffered medium is in good agreement with the value reported by Neta *et al.*⁹³.

Application of effect of ammonia/ammonium ions to atmospheric chemistry :

In semi-arid and arid regions, such as Western India, where the pH of rain water generally lies in the range 7.0-8.5²⁶, the inhibitory effect of ammonia and ammo-

Table 1. The values of rate parameters for sulfur(IV) autoxidation at 30 °C (Ref. 40)

Rate parameter	Value	Condition
k_0	$(3.2 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Unbuffered medium
	$(5.7 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Phosphate buffered medium
	$(9.7 \pm 1.5) \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Ammonia buffered medium
B	$(0.32 \pm 0.06) \times 10^2$	pH = 7.0, buffered medium
	$(2.0 \pm 0.06) \times 10^2$	pH = 7.5, buffered medium
	$(8.8 \pm 0.85) \times 10^2$	pH = 8.5, buffered medium
	$(1.7 \pm 0.4) \times 10^3$	pH = 7.6, unbuffered medium
	$(3.6 \pm 0.9) \times 10^3$	pH = 8.1, unbuffered medium
	$(15 \pm 0.6) \times 10^3$	pH = 8.5, unbuffered medium
	$(7.5 \pm 1.5) \times 10^3$	Phosphate buffered medium
$\alpha k_{\text{NH}_3}/(k_{\text{M}(n-1)} [\text{M}^{(n-1)+}])$	0.47×10^2	Phosphate buffered medium
$\alpha k_{\text{NH}_4}/(k_{\text{M}(n-1)} [\text{M}^{(n-1)+}])$	$(8.7 \pm 5.6) \times 10^4$	Unbuffered medium
$\alpha k_{\text{NH}_3}/(k_{\text{M}(n-1)} [\text{M}^{(n-1)+}])$	2.4×10^3	Unbuffered medium
$k_{\text{NH}_3}/k_{\text{NH}_4}$	1.6×10^2	Phosphate buffered medium
	0.36×10^2	Unbuffered medium
	0.5×10^2	Ref. 93
k_{NH_3}	$1.5 \times 10^7 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Ref. 93
k_{NH_4}	$3.0 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Ref. 93

niun ions on the atmospheric sulfur(IV) autoxidation is likely be the most significant. The values of pH and ammonium ion concentrations (Table 1) clearly indicate the inhibition of sulfur(IV) autoxidation to be significant particularly when $[\text{NH}_4^+]_{\text{T}}$ is high. The rearranged form of the rate law (67) was used for estimating the extent of inhibition at a desired pH.

$$R_{\text{aut}}/R_0 = 1/(1 + B [\text{inh}]_{\text{T}}) \quad (72)$$

In the absence of inhibitors, NH_3 and NH_4^+ , the ratio, R_{aut}/R_0 , shall be equal to one. However, in their presence the ratio R_{aut}/R_0 shall be less than one. The extent of its departure from unity may be used for assessing the extent of inhibition, as defined by eq. (73).

$$\text{Extent of inhibition (\%)} = (1 - R_{\text{aut}}/R_0) \times 100 \quad (73)$$

B values pertaining to unbuffered medium were used for the calculation of the extent of inhibition. These values showed the extent of inhibition by $\text{NH}_3/\text{NH}_4^+$ to be sizable, particularly when both NH_4^+ concentration and pH are high. For example, in unbuffered medium at pH = 8.1, $[\text{NH}_4^+]_{\text{T}} = 2.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, using $B = 1.7 \times 10^3$ the extent of inhibition was found to be 44%.

From this study, two inferences regarding the effect of the dissolution of NH_3 in various forms of atmospheric waters may be drawn. One, raising the pH by neutralizing acidity and two, inhibiting the rate of autoxidation through scavenging of sulfate ion radicals. Whereas,

the first would be important at all pH ranges, the second would become important only when pH is more than 7.0 and the concentrations of ammonia and ammonium ions are relatively high. The dissolution of NH_4NO_3 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ aerosols in atmospheric waters should have similar effects.

Effect of ammonia on transition metal ion catalyzed autoxidation

Copper(II)-sulfur(IV)- NH_3 - O_2 system :

To understand the chemistry of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-NH}_3\text{-S}^{\text{IV}}\text{-O}_2$ system, the kinetics of the oxidation of sulfur(IV) (to sulfate) catalyzed by amminecopper(II) complexes has been studied in the ammonia buffered solutions^{47,59}. The complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)^{2+}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_2^{2+}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_3^{2+}$ appears to be equally reactive and $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4^{2+}$ appears to be unreactive. The kinetics obeyed the rate law (74) :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{[\alpha_1 \{ \beta_1 [\text{NH}_3] + \beta_2 [\text{NH}_3]^2 + \beta_3 [\text{NH}_3]^3 \} + \gamma_1 \{ \beta_1 [\text{NH}_3] + \beta_2 [\text{NH}_3]^2 + \beta_3 [\text{NH}_3]^3 \} [\text{O}_2]}{[1 + K_{\text{SO}_3} [\text{SO}_3^{2-}] + K_{\text{OH}} [\text{OH}^-] + \beta_1 [\text{NH}_3] + \beta_2 [\text{NH}_3]^2 + \beta_3 [\text{NH}_3]^3 + \beta_4 [\text{NH}_3]^4]} \quad (74)$$

where, γ_1 and α_1 are the rate constants for O_2 -dependent

and O₂-independent pathways, respectively for Cu(NH₃)²⁺, Cu(NH₃)₂²⁺, Cu(NH₃)₃²⁺ complexes. K_{SO₃} and K_{OH} are the stability constants for CuSO₃ and CuOH complexes, respectively, and β_n are the overall stability constants for Cu(NH₃)_n complexes. Values of α₁ and γ₁ were found to be (1.32 ± 0.21) × 10⁶ L² mol⁻² s⁻¹ and (1.74 ± 0.40) × 10⁹ L³ mol⁻³ s⁻¹ respectively at 30 °C. Since the reaction rate is not influenced by the presence of ethanol – a free radical scavenger, so a non-radical mechanism appears to operate.

It is of interest to consider the intimate mechanisms of aminocopper(II)-catalysis. The order of two in S^{IV} needs an explanation, since copper(II) can oxidize only one sulfur(IV) moiety. It appears that the transition state contains one copper and two S^{IV} moieties; one sulfur(IV) is oxidized via 1-electron transfer by copper(II) and generates SO₃⁻ radical and the second sulfur(IV) moiety is oxidized in the solvent cage by an oxidant generated *in situ*. Probably, the second S^{IV} helps in electron transfer from S^{IV} to Cu^{II} by stabilizing the incipient Cu^I, as indicated by Xue *et al.*⁹⁴. This is supported by the fact that Cu^I forms a much stronger complex, CuSO₃⁻, with SO₃²⁻ than with NH₃. Since, the bound O₂ can react with S^V and with Cu^I both, two intimate mechanisms may be written as in Schemes 1 and 2.

In the Schemes 1-2, Cu^{II} represents Cu(NH₃)_n²⁺ (n = 1-3) complexes.

our results to Jaipur city, showed ammonia not to affect the rate due to formation of Cu(NH₃)_n²⁺ complexes, which operates through a non-radical mechanism, since the major Cu^{II} species shall be CuSO₃ and so the autoxidation reaction shall proceed via a radical mechanism. So ammonia will work as an inhibitor under conditions of high pH.

Nickel(II)-sulfur(IV)-NH₃-O₂ system :

In Ni^{II}-S^{IV}-O₂ system in the region of pH > 8.4 both Ni^{II} and S^{IV} are simultaneously autoxidized, and when sulfur is consumed fully NiOOH precipitates⁴⁷. At pH > 8.4, ethanol has no effect on the rate whereas ammonia strongly inhibits the reaction when pH > 7.0. The kinetics of the reaction, in both the presence and the absence of ethanol, is defined by the rate law :

$$\frac{d[S^{IV}]}{dt} = \frac{\left([Ni^{II}]_T - \frac{K_{sp}F}{[OH^-]^2} \right) kK_o[O_2]}{1 + K_o[O_2]} \quad (75)$$

where *k* is the rate constant, K_o is the equilibrium constant for the adsorption of O₂ on -Ni(OH)₂ particle surface. In ammonia buffer, the factor *F* is defined by eq. (76) :

$$F = (1 + K_{SO_3}[SO_3^{2-}] + K_{OH}[OH^-] + K_1[NH_3] + K_1K_2[NH_3]^2 + K_1K_2K_3[NH_3]^3 + K_1K_2K_3K_4[NH_3]^4) \quad (76)$$

where K_{SO₃}, K_{OH}, K₁, K₂, K₃ and K₄ are the stability

Scheme 1

The results of this study are useful in understanding the atmospheric chemistry of aqueous phase autoxidation of dissolved sulfur dioxide in copper(II)-ammonia-sulfur(IV)-oxygen system at high pH. An application of

constants of NiSO₃, NiOH⁺, Ni(NH₃)²⁺, Ni(NH₃)₂²⁺, Ni(NH₃)₃²⁺ and Ni(NH₃)₄²⁺, respectively. In unbuffered medium, the factor *F* reduces to eq. (77) :

$$F = (1 + K_{SO_3}[SO_3^{2-}] + K_{OH}[OH^-]) \quad (77)$$

Scheme 2

The values of k and K_{sp} were found to be $(1.3 \pm 0.08) \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $(4.2 \pm 3.5) 10^{-16}$, respectively at 30 °C. A non radical mechanism, which assumes the adsorption of both SO_3^{2-} and O_2 on the $-\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ particle surface, has been proposed. At $\text{pH} \leq 8.2$, Ni^{II} displays no catalytic activity for sulfur(IV)-autoxidation and it is also not oxidized to NiOOH .

While the ammonia strongly inhibits the uncatalyzed reaction, its effect on metal ion catalyzed reaction depends upon the reactivity and concentration of metal-ammonia complexes. For the particular case of copper(II) and Ni^{II} catalyses, the effect of ammonia depends upon pH and ammonia concentration.

Effect of volatile organic compounds (VOCs)

Alaya and Backstrom⁹⁵ reported the inhibiting effect of alcohols on sulfur(IV) autoxidation. Subsequently, the effect of several inhibitors⁹⁵ such as alcohols, organic acids, benzene, toluene, naphthalene, paraffin oil, α -pinene, *cis*-verbenol, *sobrerol*, *myrtenol*, etc. has been studied on S^{IV} autoxidation. The organics are known to scavenge the SO_4^- radical and break the autoxidation chain (78) re-sulting in the inhibition of the sulfur(IV) autoxidation.

Detailed studies on this aspect are in progress.

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